

Diversity **E**quity **I**nclusion

Managing Diversity in Smaller European Businesses:

Comparative Analysis

2024-2025

Contributions

While the report is written by several colleagues, the survey has been developed, reviewed, tested and data collected by collective work of many within the DEI4SME project team. We briefly mention key contributions of all colleagues who were involved in implementing WP2, Activity 1 (Survey on DEI challenges for the under-represented groups), Activity 2 (Survey on DEI challenges for the SMEs), and Activity 5 (Report on DEI management in SME context framework).

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Definitions of the Main Concepts Used in the Surveys and this Report

Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) is a conceptual framework that promotes the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially populations that have historically been underrepresented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc.

- **Diversity** refers to the representation or composition of various social identity groups in a work group, organization, or community.

- **Equity** involves providing resources according to the need to help diverse populations achieve their highest state of health and other functioning.

- **Inclusion** strives for an environment that offers affirmation, celebration, and appreciation of different approaches, styles, perspectives, and experiences.

Diversity & Identifications Explored:

Gender identity refers to one's deeply felt sense of being male, female, both, neither, or anywhere along the gender spectrum.

Belonging to the LGBTQIA+ community refers to an individual's lasting pattern of emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction to individuals of the same gender, different genders, or multiple genders.

Age refers to the length of time that an individual has lived or existed since birth.

Language refers to systems of communication used by humans to convey meaning through a combination of sounds, symbols, and gestures. An individual's native language refers to the language learned from birth. **Accent** refers to the distinct patterns of pronunciation, intonations, and speech characteristics associated with speakers or a particular language or dialect.

Caregiving refers to the provision of assistance, support, and care to individuals who are unable to fully care for themselves due to age, illness, disability, or other circumstances.

Education here refers to different types and contexts. Formal education: primary education, secondary education, higher education. Vocational education: vocational training programs, apprenticeship.

Religion refers to a system of beliefs, practices, rituals, and moral values centred around the worship of a divine or supernatural being.

Students or those with little previous work experience refers to one's current educational path (student) or one's who recently graduated and/or one's feeling that their work experience is minimal.

Ethnic background refers to one's affiliation with a group based on shared social, cultural (e.g. language, religion, food, or heritage), and historical experiences derived from a common national or regional background. Ethnic groups are distinguished by their specific beliefs, values, behaviors, and sense of belonging. Individuals may identify with multiple ethnicities.

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3 Overview of the DEI management from SME and individual perspectives

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Executive Summary

Managing Diversity in Smaller European Businesses: Comparative Analysis

Two parallel surveys – one for SME owners/managers, other for employees – in Austria, Finland, Germany and Lithuania reveal that diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) is more of an expressed goal than a set practice. Most firms consider themselves “aware/compliant”, but formal roles, metrics and mentoring schemes are still the exception; many managers admit they are “just compliant” or even unsure where they stand. Formal DEI job titles are rare, yet roughly half of the employees assume someone is looking after the topic and issues, hinting at weak sign-posting rather than total neglect. Every country reports clear rules for pointing out harassment, but everyday supports such as mentoring, progress tracking and staff input are lacking and noticed by workers even less than by managers. Age, gender and language differences are widely recognised, but by contrast more marginalized identities are largely unrecorded especially in management roles, and many respondents simply “don’t know” who is present. Overall, the findings indicate good intentions but struggles following through.

3.1 Overview of Data and Comparative Approach

In both surveys we have a distribution among respondents in relation to the location of the head offices of their companies where they work or which they are represented. SME survey has a more unified distribution among Austria, Germany, Finland, and Lithuania, whereas in individual survey we have most responses from Lithuania. As of company size, SME survey covers companies with size that adheres to the SME definition having less than 250 employees (91.2%), whereas the individual respondents cover a broader variety of company sizes, ranging from <250 employees (62.2%) to >250 employees (35.1%). As intended, more than half of the respondents in the SME survey are top or mid-level managers (64.2%) and in the individual survey we cover non-management position (56.2%).

It is important to note that **the findings in this chapter are based on two distinct surveys** conducted among small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) representatives and individual employees across Austria, Germany, Finland, and Lithuania. Importantly, **the samples are not directly matched**: individual respondents are not employed in the same organizations as the SME representatives. Therefore, comparisons between the two groups should be interpreted as indicative of broader cross-national trends rather than intra-organizational. For the SME survey, companies were categorized by the location of their head offices, while individuals were grouped based on their country of residence. This discrepancy in geographic categorization introduces additional context-related variation that may influence perceptions of DEI practices and culture.

Additionally, the SME survey had a substantially smaller sample size than the individual survey, due to which its findings are more susceptible to random variation and less likely to reflect the broader population. When interpreting joint conclusions from both surveys, this limitation should be considered, especially in cross-country comparisons where the SME data may distort or exaggerate results.

There are also structural differences between the two samples. The SME survey achieved a more balanced distribution across all four countries, whereas in the individual survey slightly more responses came from Lithuania (30.19%). In terms of organizational scale, the SME data aligns with the European Commission's definition of small and medium-sized enterprises as 91.2% of companies surveyed had fewer than 250 employees. Conversely, the individual respondent pool reflected a wider range of company sizes, with 62.2% working in SMEs and 35.1% in larger organizations. Furthermore, the SME survey predominantly reflects managerial perspectives, with 64.2% of respondents holding top or mid-level management roles. The individual survey captures experiences from lower hierarchical levels, with 56.2% of respondents in non-management roles. While a subset of questions was designed to allow for comparison between the two surveys, differences in sample composition and organizational context should be taken into account when interpreting the results.

Finally, the data visualization approach used throughout this report consolidates Likert scale responses by merging "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" categories. While this improves readability and facilitates cross-group comparisons, it reduces response granularity and may obscure differences in the intensity of agreement. Such simplification should be interpreted cautiously, particularly when assessing the depth of sentiment across groups (Harpe, 2015). Overall, the results offer valuable insights into perceived DEI conditions across sectors and countries but should be understood within the constraints of the survey design and sampling strategy (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018¹).

3.2 Maturity

The results from the survey reveal some differences between SME representatives and individual respondents regarding the maturity of DEI in companies across Austria, Germany, Finland, and Lithuania.

When trying to understand the level of maturity of DEI management in a company, it is worthwhile asking whether the respondents, as a part of a company, feel that DEI is a part of the company's identity. The statement "*DEI is a part of our company's identity*" received significantly more agreement from individuals than from SME representatives in Austria and Germany (Figure 1). In Austria, 38% of individual respondents agreed with the statement, compared to only 26% of SMEs. In Germany, this difference was even more pronounced (individuals – 27%, SMEs – 7%). Interestingly, in Finland, both groups reported nearly identical levels of agreement (38%),

¹ Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE

indicating a shared understanding of DEI's importance. In Lithuania more SMEs (36%) than individuals (32%) identified DEI as part of their company identity.

Figure 1. DEI is a part of our company's identity (SME and Individual)

Additional to DEI in company identity, it is important to take certain measures. In this case, appoint as person responsible for managing DEI issues in the company (Figure 2). SME representatives commonly indicate that their companies do not have a designated person responsible for DEI-related matters. In contrast, individual respondents reported that, on average, approximately half of the companies have someone assigned to DEI responsibilities. This may suggest that although formal DEI roles are uncommon in SMEs, DEI responsibilities are often integrated into existing HR function, which may not be clearly communicated or formally recognized.

Figure 2. Nominated person responsible for DEI related issues (SME and Individual)

Next graph presents a more nuanced picture of DEI maturity using six predefined levels (that were explained to the respondents) (Figure 3). Most common level where companies attribute themselves or the individuals see their employers positioned are being DEI aware and DEI compliant. Individual respondents, on average, see their employers slightly higher in this maturity ranking, attributing DEI Expert and Advanced in DEI on average 3,5% and 7,7% respectively more than SME representatives. This suggests a general perception that DEI practices are still developing and far from being fully institutionalized. On the other hand, a notable proportion of SME respondents reported a Lack of DEI Awareness, suggesting significant gaps in organizational cognition of DEI-related issues.

Figure 3. DEI maturity (SME and Individual)

Figure 4 presents comparative results evaluating the extent to which diverse perspectives are encouraged and valued in both strategic and daily decision-making. Both parts of the graph show similar situations across countries including diverse perspectives into strategic and daily decisions. The graph highlights consistent variations in valuing and encouraging diverse perspectives across company and individual levels. Germany emerges as a clear leader in aligning company diversity objectives with employee experience, suggesting effective DEI practices integrated into organizational culture and everyday interactions. Lithuanian companies also indicate strong organizational policies, though the slight gap at the individual level signals room for improvement. Austria and Finland show consistently lower agreement levels, particularly at individual levels, indicating critical areas where diversity strategies may need refinement and closer alignment with employee perceptions.

Figure 4. Diverse perspectives (SME and Individual)

The comparison between SME and Individual surveys highlight some possible discussion points. Indeed, differences between SME representatives' and individual respondents' views on DEI as part of their organizational identity suggest gaps in communication or alignment. In Austria and particularly Germany, individuals perceive DEI as more integral to their companies' identity compared to SMEs' views, implying that employees might recognize informal or implicit DEI practices not formally acknowledged by company management. In Lithuania, the opposite is observed, raising questions about possible overestimations by SMEs regarding their DEI integration or insufficient awareness at the employee level. Interestingly, Finland shows alignment between SMEs and individuals, which may indicate a shared organisational culture or more transparent DEI communication strategies. Moreover, despite limited formal appointments of DEI-specific roles in SMEs, individuals commonly acknowledge that DEI responsibilities are managed, underscoring the significance of explicit recognition and communication of such roles. Finally, varied levels of maturity and differing perceptions about the inclusion of diverse perspectives in decision-making reveal that while countries like Germany have achieved strong

alignment between DEI policies and practices, others face critical challenges in effectively translating DEI strategies into employees' daily experiences. Thus, these findings underline the importance of not only establishing DEI frameworks but also ensuring their visibility, explicit communication, and meaningful integration into organisational culture and operations.

3.3 Practices

This subchapter presents a comparative analysis of SME representatives' and individual respondents' perspectives on DEI practices within companies of sample countries. The following graphs provide insights into how employees are involved in decision-making processes, what DEI management practices are implemented, and how diversity is managed in daily organizational life.

In previous section statement about diversity appreciation in strategic and daily-decision making was analysed. This section provides a deeper understanding whether companies truly involve employees and welcomes their perspective in decision-making process. Figure 5 indicates, that across most sample countries, a larger proportion of SME representatives report involving employees occasionally rather than frequently. For instance, in Germany, 84% of SMEs report occasional involvement, while only 13% report frequent involvement. Individual respondents, particularly in Finland (72%) and Austria (56%), tend to indicate more frequent involvement than SMEs report. Interestingly, the percentage of respondents stating "no involvement" is higher among individuals than SME representatives in Austria (33% vs. 17%), suggesting a potential misalignment between perceived and actual employee participation.

Figure 5. Employee involvement in decision-making (SME and Individual)

Couple of important and often mentioned good DEI management practices involve building a culture of inclusion (Figure 6). For that reason, safe space and difference appreciation are significant. Across countries, most SME representatives believe that management provides a safe

space for sharing opinions, especially in Germany (92%) and Lithuania (91%). However, individual perceptions are more modest (around 50-70% across countries), again suggesting a gap between managerial views and employee experience. When it comes to practicing differences openly, responses are more aligned between SMEs and individuals. Lithuania stands out with consistently high agreement across both statements and respondent groups, whereas Germany shows a notable drop between SME and individual perspectives, particularly regarding openness to practice differences (SMEs 90%, Individuals 60%).

Figure 6. Practices of creating safe space and practicing differences (SME and Individual)

Figure 7 illustrates the presence of DEI-related structures and practices within organizations. Overall, the most commonly acknowledged practice among SMEs is employee familiarization with how to report discrimination or harassment. Austria (75%) and Germany (70%) report the highest values for this indicator at the SME level. However, individuals across all countries report lower levels of awareness than SMEs, hinting at a possible communication gap. The existence of mentorship programs and monitoring processes is reported less frequently by both groups, with Lithuania showing relatively higher implementation levels in both categories. In contrast, Austria and Germany show the lowest levels of mentorship programs, particularly from the SME perspective (below 10%). Notably, Lithuanian respondents from both SMEs and individual groups indicate a relatively uniform understanding of DEI management practices across all categories. This alignment might be attributed to formal regulatory requirements in Lithuania, where employees must be introduced to specific workplace policies and legal documents when starting a new position. These mandatory onboarding practices may contribute to greater awareness and perceived consistency in DEI structures among Lithuanian respondents.

Figure 7. DEI management practices (SME and Individual)

The comparative analysis highlights several discrepancies between SME representatives and individual employees regarding the implementation and perception of DEI practices. SMEs often report higher levels of DEI-related engagement and structures than their employees recognise, particularly in areas such as decision-making involvement and formal processes for addressing discrimination. This suggests that while many SMEs may have DEI mechanisms in place, they may not be sufficiently visible or communicated to employees. Lithuania consistently demonstrates stronger alignment between SME and individual responses, indicating potentially more transparent or embedded DEI practices. Conversely, Austria and Germany show more pronounced gaps, suggesting a need to enhance internal communication and employee engagement in DEI processes. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of not only implementing DEI policies but also ensuring their clarity, accessibility, and effectiveness from the perspective of all organizational members.

3.4 Inclusion/diversity

This section compares responses from SME representatives and individual respondents on how different dimensions of diversity are perceived to be represented among employees and managers in companies. The analysis is based on reported recognition of ten diversity dimensions: gender, LGBTQIA identity, age, language, caregiver status, education, religion, disability, student status, and ethnicity.

As shown in Figure 8, most respondents agree that age, education, gender, and language are the most visible diversity dimensions in their workplaces. In Germany and Lithuania in particular, SME representatives report extremely high levels of diversity in these areas (often exceeding 90%). In contrast, representation in dimensions such as disability, LGBTQIA identity, and religion is

reported far less frequently across all countries and both respondent groups. Interestingly, Lithuania and Germany report consistently higher levels of perceived diversity across most dimensions than Austria and Finland. In Lithuania, both SMEs and individuals report strong representation in nearly all categories, suggesting a broader recognition or possibly greater actual diversity. Austria and Finland tend to show more modest recognition of diversity, with greater variation between SME and individual perspectives.

Figure 8. Diversity among employees (SME and Individual)

Figure 9 reveals a noticeably different picture regarding diversity in managerial positions. Across all countries and diversity categories, reported diversity among managers is significantly lower than among employees. While age and education remain the most visible characteristics, dimensions such as LGBTQIA identity, religion, disability, and ethnicity appear to be particularly underrepresented in leadership roles. The data show some divergence between SMEs and individual respondents. In Austria, individual respondents tend to report more diversity among managers than SME representatives do, suggesting that non-managerial staff may observe greater diversity or be more attuned to inclusive practices than those in managerial positions. This contrasts with Germany, where SME representatives report higher diversity levels than individuals, possibly reflecting optimism bias or limited visibility of diversity in leadership from employees' perspectives.

In contrast, SMEs in Finland appear to have a slightly more positive outlook on managerial diversity, particularly in traditional or visible categories (gender, age, education), whereas individuals perceive more diversity in the less-visible dimensions (e.g., disability, ethnicity). However, the differences are not drastic, suggesting relatively aligned perceptions overall. In Lithuania, non-managerial employees are significantly more likely than SME representatives to perceive diversity among managers. This might indicate either greater awareness of day-to-day interactions with diverse leaders or that managerial self-perception underestimates the presence of diversity.

Figure 9. Diversity among managers (SME and Individual)

The “don’t know” responses shown in Figure 10 are particularly revealing, offering insight into employees’ and managers’ awareness of diversity within their organizations. Across all countries and both respondent groups, a substantial proportion of individuals and SME representatives indicated uncertainty about whether specific diversity dimensions are represented among employees and managers. In Germany, Finland, and Lithuania SME respondents selected “don’t know” when asked about the presence of diversity in categories such as LGBTQIA identity and religion. Among individual respondents, the rates are often even higher, suggesting that non-managerial employees may feel less informed or less confident in identifying whether certain diversity characteristics are present in their companies. Austrian respondents felt more confident when recognising diversity dimensions both among SME and individual respondents, going slightly above 20% of “don’t know” option for LGBTQIA and religion dimensions.

A noteworthy case is Lithuania. While both SME and individual respondents in Lithuania previously reported high levels of diversity across most categories, the “don’t know” responses paint a more complex picture. Lithuanian individual respondents express some of the highest uncertainty across all countries, especially regarding LGBTQIA identity (about 40–50% for employees, even higher for management), religion, and disability. This suggests that while diversity may be present, its visibility and communication within companies are not equally distributed across roles. Employees may not feel empowered or informed enough to recognise diversity, more in less visible or more sensitive categories.

Figure 10. Diversity among employees, Don't know (SME and Individual)

Figure 11. Diversity among managers, Don't know (SME and Individual)

In stipulation, this contrast of high reported diversity alongside high uncertainty may be explained by several factors, including limited opportunities for open dialogue, cultural norms that discourage discussion of personal characteristics, or unclear communication of diversity-related policies. Furthermore, in contexts like Lithuania, where onboarding procedures are often formal and standardised, employees may be familiar with institutional documents but still lack day-to-day exposure or understanding of how diversity manifests in practice, especially in leadership positions. These findings raise important questions about transparency and awareness. The high level of uncertainty, particularly in relation to protected or less visible identity dimensions, suggests that DEI efforts may not be sufficiently communicated, measured, or openly discussed. This underlines the need for better internal communication, employee engagement, and inclusive leadership practices to ensure that all organizational members, regardless of position, are aware of the company’s diversity landscape and feel that diversity is recognized and valued in practice not just on paper.

To summarise, the analysis confirms that while some aspects of diversity (such as age and education) are widely recognised, others, specifically those involving protected or less visible characteristics, are either underrepresented or unknown. This discrepancy is even more pronounced at the managerial level, where reported diversity is significantly lower across nearly all categories. The high incidence of “don’t know” responses, especially among managers, signals a lack of comprehensive diversity tracking and possibly a discomfort or lack of confidence in addressing certain identity dimensions. These findings emphasise the importance of building internal awareness, promoting open dialogue, and creating mechanisms that allow diversity to be better understood, respected, and integrated at all organizational levels.

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